

MARV DASHT PROJECT
ANSWERS

83 Brattle Street, Apt. # 43
Cambridge, Mass. 02138
July 31st, 1976

Dear Bill,

In all my high level organization I have just come across, in a stack of papers, a letter I almost wrote you early last spring. It basically concerned your Marv Dasht material, since Kim Maurer had been asking me (?) (and Andrew's father as well, who was somewhat upset since, not knowing, he thought it was some part of Andrew's material) about it. Now that she is working near Hissar, I guess it is mostly not relevant.

However, just to be sure that the situation is clear:
I assume you know that there are seven drawers of your Marv Dasht stuff in the Narenjestan "archaeological lab" basement sherd storage. They are labelled: Crates 1 & 2; Crates 2 & 3; Crates 4 & 5; Crates 6 & 7; Crates 10 & 12; and two just marked "MD". They are the collection which you had given Andrew to study and from which he gave you his dating list. There are also, I think, a few tiny bags in with his 34 crates of stuff in Teheran. These would be things he pulled for their greater interest and further study or comparison.

I have committed myself to publishing Andrew's work, but I have considered the Marv Dasht material (as he did) to be all yours and basically finished in terms of further study, publication, or whatever. My God! There is more than enough to do with all the rest!!! I have recently heard from Don that he is working with some aspects of it anyway.

I heard the rumour from Kim that Shirley Jarman has made some sort of policy statement that collections will be held for only two years. After which I don't quite know what she has in mind -- perhaps she is planning to chuck it all out?? Perhaps that should be clarified if you are in Shiraz and see her -- not that I have any great attachment to sherd collections, but they do represent a great expenditure of time, money, etc. even if not very pretty or excessively well organized; and still very useful, if one is prepared to spend the time and energy to work through them. Since I have the whole collection of my Dolatabad stuff and a lot of Andrew's coastal material there (both of which I will undoubtedly need to take another look at again) I would like to know its "Final resting place" -- even if the Shiraz city dump.

- My only requests concerning the Marv Dasht material are:
- 1) Could you sometime send me a copy of the "report" or whatever write up Andrew gave you. I will need, with your permission, to take a long look at the material in Shiraz in comparison with that list, since it is one of the rare ways that I can get a handle on much of his mental typology.
 - 2) That the material in Teheran be left there until I have the opportunity to work through it and attempt to reconstruct Andrew's reasoning as to its importance and its comparison to the material it is stored with. I may then, with your permission, need to publish a few comments on its relationships etc. But this is, I guess still several years into the black and murky future. I pray Don will have the Istakhr publication done by then, for that should help immensely.

How goes life in Columbus? I hear you will be out at Malyan again this fall. Will you be at the Munich/Nice "zoos" (or already in the field?)? If so, I hope to see you there. I'm giving papers at both (Horrors!! Quivers in the pit of the tummy!) Would you believe -- "The Development of Irrigation Agriculture in the Highlands of Southern Iran" An awfully high-faluting title for a mangy area of only 4 sq. km. of 4th mill. fields. I'm still only drafting up the maps for it! (Normal rush state I seem to live in) And had better hurry up and do some high powered hallucinations so that I can get the papers written. I'm scheduled to leave for England in only two weeks! Another quiver of Horrors!!

Sometime this winter, I pray, my thesis will be finally finished, and then I must rush into getting Andrew's stuff going, or it will hang around my neck for years!!

Have you any suggestions for post doc. grants or any other source(s) of funding which would keep me alive (guess for about a year, and maybe at least partly in England and Iran) and in pen points and typing paper while working up his notes and collections for publication?

Do keep in touch -- perhaps we will meet in September --

With best wishes,

Martha

P.S. I'm back here from September 20th or so, should you ever be coming through! If (???)my "current pattern" continues I am not generally spending nights here, so I can even offer you a free pad to yourself!